

A Retrospective Study of Cesarean Hysterectomy Cases at a Tertiary Health Care Centre in BiharSurabhi¹, Kumari Nutan², Minu Sharan³¹Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, PMCH, Patna²Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, PMCH, Patna³Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, PMCH, Patna

Received: 25-09-2024 / Revised: 23-10-2024 / Accepted: 26-11-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Cesarean hysterectomy is defined as surgical removal of the uterus at the time of Cesarean delivery. It is considered a near miss event and is performed as a last resort to control potentially fatal postpartum hemorrhage. Uterine atony is the most common cause of PPH which accounts for 70%-80% of the cases. With the use of multiple uterotonic drugs and other conservative methods, the need to do hysterectomy in cases of atonic PPH has reduced. Placenta accreta spectrum and uterine rupture are the major contributor to cesarean hysterectomy cases nowadays because of the increasing cesarean section rates. The purpose of this study is to understand the risk factors leading to Cesarean Hysterectomy along with the analysis of the causes, morbidity, mortality and perinatal outcome associated with it.

Aim and Objective: To determine the incidence, risk factor and fetomaternal outcome of cesarean hysterectomy cases at PMCH, Patna

Method: A Retrospective observational study was conducted and all the cases of caesarean hysterectomy performed at PMCH, Patna between Jan 2022 and Dec 2023 were studied. Data regarding demographic characteristics, indications, risk factors, complications and perinatal outcome was collected from medical records and the results analysed.

Result: Total number of deliveries during the study period was 9032. Total number of caesarean hysterectomy was 78. The incidence of caesarean hysterectomy was 8.6/1000 deliveries. In my study, the most common indication was Ruptured uterus (65.3%) followed by morbidly adhered placenta (15.3%), Placenta previa (12.8%) and atonic PPH (6.4%).

Conclusion: Cesarean Hysterectomy is a technically challenging procedure with high complication rates. So, proper antenatal check-up along with close monitoring of high risk pregnancies and institutional delivery is important to curb the high rates of caesarean hysterectomy.

Keywords: Cesarean Hysterectomy, Postpartum Hemorrhage (PPH), Uterine Atony, Placenta Accreta Spectrum (PAS), Uterine Rupture, Obstetric Complications, Maternal Mortality, Perinatal Outcome.

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Introduction

Cesarean hysterectomy is defined as surgical removal of uterus at the time of Cesarean delivery. It is considered a near miss event and is performed as a last resort to control potentially fatal postpartum hemorrhage. It is a technically challenging procedure owing to the physiological changes of pregnancy in the pelvic organs. The vessels that supply the uterus, ovaries, and bladder are substantially larger and more tortuous in pregnancy than they are in the nonpregnant state. Meticulous care in the manipulation of clamps, cutting of pedicles, and placement of sutures is required to prevent severe bleeding. Edema of the structures surrounding the uterus allows easy dissection of surgical planes but produces large

pedicles from which blood vessels may escape. Special attention must be given to the proper size of pedicles and careful hemostatic suturing techniques. Adhesions due to previous surgeries further complicates the procedure and increases the chances of bladder injury. Uterine atony is the most common cause of PPH which accounts for 70% - 80% of cases [3]. With the use of multiple uterotonic drugs and other conservative methods like intrauterine balloon tamponade, uterine compression sutures and systematic pelvic devascularization, the need to do hysterectomy in cases of atonic PPH has reduced. However, hysterectomy can only be lifesaving if it is attempted at right time. Conversely, if performed

when conservative measures could have been attempted, it could result in more harm. Placenta accreta spectrum (PAS) is rare, but its incidence is increasing due to a rise in Caesarean section rates [4,5]. PAS is an abnormal trophoblastic invasion into the myometrium, up to the serosa, or more [5]. Abnormally adhered placenta is frequently diagnosed intraoperatively when an attempt to remove placenta has been made and massive PPH starts. Timely decision to undertake hysterectomy in such cases is vital.

Another major cause requiring cesarean hysterectomy is uterine rupture which is defined as disruption in the continuity of all the uterine layers anytime beyond 28 weeks of pregnancy.

The prevalence was found significantly higher in under developed countries of Asia and Africa in comparison to high income countries [6]. Uterine rupture after prior cesarean section is becoming more common as the availability of cesarean section increases in these settings [7].

A clean scar rupture may be amenable to repair. But, spontaneous non obstructive rupture which usually involves the fundus and obstructive rupture which usually involves lateral uterine wall requires hysterectomy.

The purpose of this study is to understand the risk factors leading to Cesarean Hysterectomy along with the analysis of the causes, morbidity, mortality and perinatal outcome associated with it.

Material and Methods

A Retrospective observational study was conducted and all the cases of cesarean hysterectomy performed at PMCH, PATNA between Jan 2022 and Dec 2023 were studied. Data regarding demographic characteristics, indications, risk factors, complications and perinatal outcome was collected from medical records.

Inclusion Criteria

All pregnant women with Period of Gestation > 28 weeks who underwent Cesarean hysterectomy at PMCH Patna.

Exclusion Criteria

- Cases referred to PMCH after cesarean hysterectomy done outside the institute.
- Hysterectomy done at period of Gestation < 28 weeks.

Results and Analysis

Table 1: Incidence

Total no of deliveries	9032
Total no of caesarean hysterectomy	78
Incidence	8.6/1000 deliveries

Total number of deliveries during the study period was 9032. Total number of caesarean hysterectomy was 78. The incidence of caesarean hysterectomy was 8.6/1000 deliveries

Table 2: Age

Age (years)	No of patients	Percentage (n=78)
<20	01	0.8%
21-25	34	43.1%
26-30	29	37.2%
>30	14	17.9%
Mean	28.1 years	

Table 3: Parity

Parity	No of patients	Percentage (n=78)
P1	5	6.9%
P2	28	35.9%
P3	25	31.5%
P4	16	20.5%
>P4	04	5.1%

Table 4: Period of Gestation

POG (weeks)	No of patients	Percentage (n=78)
<34	29	37.2%
>34	49	62.8%

Table 5: Indication

Indication	No of patients	Percentage
Ruptured uterus	51	65.4%
Placenta accrete	12	15.4%
Placenta previa	10	12.8%
Atonic PPH	05	6.4%

Table 6: History of Previous Uterine Surgery

Previous uterine surgery	No. of patients	Percentage (n=78)
h/o prev LSCS	42	53.8%
h/o prev LSCS+ D and E	08	10.3%
h/o hysterotomy	01	1.3%
h/o uterine perforation	01	1.3%
h/o D and E	04	5.1%
Total	56	71.8%

Table 7: Complications

Complication	No of patients	Percentage
Paralytic ileus	11	14.1%
Febrile illness	10	12.8%
Wound complication	07	8.9%
Bladder injury	06	7.6%
Acute renal failure	05	6.4%
DIC	02	2.6%
Mortality	09	11.5%

Table 8: Fetal Outcome

Fetal outcome	No of patients	Percentage
Live birth	23	29.4%
Still birth	53	67.9%
Death within 1 week	2	2.6%
Perinatal mortality	54	69.2%

Discussion

Overall incidence of cesarean hysterectomy in our institution was 8.6/1000 deliveries which is similar to Lovina et al (0.87%) [8]. It is lower than that reported by Amudha et al (1.01%) [9]. Lower incidence was reported from India by Jaya Chawla et al (0.8/1000) [10], Swati et al (0.047%) [11] and Dobroslava et al (0.12%) [12]. The higher rate of emergency obstetric hysterectomy at our center is because PMCH is the apex institution of the state and complicated cases from far away locations are brought in a very critical state with various comorbidities who have minimal or no ANC checkups. The mean age of patients was 28.1 years with 42% of patients in the age group 21-25 years. This young age at hysterectomy in association with high parity is attributed to young age at marriage and childbearing in our country. In our study, 93.5 % of the patients were multipara out of which 5.1% were grand multipara. This shows that multiparity is a risk factor for obstetric hemorrhage. Out of 51 patients with uterine rupture, scarred uterus was present in 36 (70.6%) cases with history of previous LSCS in 32 (62.7%) cases, history of uterine perforation in 1 case and history of

hysterotomy in 1 case. In placenta accreta all 12 (100%) patients had scarred uterus with H/O previous Cesarean section in 10 (83.3%) patients. In cases with placenta previa 7 (70%) out of 10 cases had scarred uterus with cesarean section in 6 (60%) cases. This indicates that risk of ruptured uterus and abnormal placentation increases significantly with previous cesarean section [4,5]. In our study, the most common indication was Ruptured uterus (65.3%) followed by morbidly adhered placenta (15.3%), Placenta praevia (12.8%) and atonic PPH (6.4%). In some Indian studies the most common cause is ruptured uterus (46% by Vara Lakshmi et al)[13], 50% by Nooren et al[14] while some studies reported atonic PPH to be the most common cause (75% by Jayabharthi [15] and 59.8% by Bhaskaran et al [16]). Other studies also reported morbidly adherent placenta to be the most common cause (38.8% by Swati et al [11] and 44.4% by Dobroslava et al [12]). Patients are brought to our hospital from far away areas after being in labour for many hours leading to obstructive rupture or severe atonic PPH. Also, lack of understanding about the possible risk of rupture in trial of VBAC at home leads to higher

rate of ruptured uterus and subsequent hysterectomy at PMCH.

In our study, maternal mortality was 11.5% which was similar to a study by Amudha et al (10.3%) [9]. VaraLakshmi (14.28%) [13], Nooren et al (15%) [14] And Swati et al (19.44%) [11] Reported a higher incidence where Dobroslava (1.9%) [12] and Ahmad (3%) [18] Observed a low incidence. Acute haemorrhagic crisis superimposed on patients with severe anemia and other pre-existing untreated medical disorders leads to high mortality in such cases. Febrile illness was seen in 10 patients which is similar to study by Wani et al (12.9%) [17].

Postoperative Paralytic ileus was seen in 14.1% cases which is similar to a study by Jayabharthi (17.8%) [15]. both of these complications were managed conservatively by antibiotics, adequate hydration, and antipyretics and all of the patients recovered by these measures.

Other complications were bladder injury in 6.4% of cases, wound infection in 8.9% of cases, acute renal failure in 3.8% of cases and DIC in 2.6% of cases. All of the patients required blood transfusion with vasopressor requirement in 44.9 % of patients. Perinatal mortality (69%) was very high in our study. This is because majority of cases were of ruptured uterus with fetal demise at admission.

Conclusion

Cesarean Hysterectomy is a technically challenging procedure with high complication rates. In addition to this, loss of fertility and menstrual function has profound psychosocial effect on women's life. So, proper antenatal check-up along with close monitoring of high risk pregnancies and institutional delivery is important to curb the high rates of cesarean hysterectomy.

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